

Asynchronous-fork: Mitigating Long Latency and Low Throughput of In-Memory Key-Value Stores When Taking A Snapshot of In-Memory Data

Supplementary materials for rebuttal

#390

1 (Reviewer B) Complexity

In Stage 2 of Fig. 5 of our manuscript, a synchronization mechanism is introduced to copy the to-be-modified PTEs to the child process. Note that once the synchronization is triggered, the parent process has to stop serving queries. Specifically, if the synchronization is performed by the parent process (our current implementation), it is trapped in the kernel mode; if the synchronization is performed by the child process, the parent process needs to wait until all to-be-modified PTEs are copied.

Implementing an efficient synchronization mechanism faces two critical problems: 1) **All possible PTE modifications should be captured**, in order to ensure consistency strictly. 2) **Unnecessary synchronization should be eliminated**, in order to achieve higher performance.

For the former problem, the difficulty here is that many operations modify PTEs in different ways or function call paths (see Table 1 in the manuscript). We therefore make a comprehensive analysis on Linux kernel and hook the related functions.

For the latter problem, there are some trade-offs involved in how to check if the PTEs have been copied. An intuitive approach is to set a flag for each PTE to track its status. However, such an approach incurs high cost because some operations may modify a large VMA while traversing all the VMA's PTEs is prohibitively expensive. Instead, we set a flag on the PMD entry to quickly identify if corresponding 512 PTEs have been copied. Note that setting the flag on the upper page table entry (e.g., PUD entry) is not a better idea. This is because a PUD entry indexes 262, 144 PTEs and synchronizing them takes 10ms.

2 (Reviewer C) Data Leakage Caused by Stale TLB Entry

Private Page Table				Shared Page Table			
Step	OP	Parent (P)	Child (C)	Step	OP	Parent (P)	Child (C)
1	Initial state	TLB: V → X PTE: V → X	TLB: V → X PTE: V → X	1	Initial state	TLB: V → X PTE: V → X	TLB: V → X PTE: V → X
2	P: Set PTE → none present	TLB: V → X PTE: V → N	TLB: V → X PTE: V → X	2	P: Set PTE → none present	TLB: V → X PTE: V → N	TLB: V → X PTE: V → N
3	P: TLB flush	TLB: N/A PTE: V → N	TLB: V → X PTE: V → X	3	P: TLB flush	TLB: N/A PTE: V → N	TLB: V → X PTE: V → N
4	C: Set PTE → none present	TLB: N/A PTE: V → N	TLB: V → X PTE: V → N	4	C: skipped because N ≠ X	TLB: N/A PTE: V → N	TLB: V → X PTE: V → N
5	C: TLB flush	TLB: N/A PTE: V → N	TLB: N/A PTE: V → N	5	P: Update PTE	TLB: N/A PTE: V → Y	TLB: V → X PTE: V → Y
6	P: Update PTE	TLB: N/A PTE: V → Y	TLB: N/A PTE: V → N	6	P/C: Access V	TLB: V → Y PTE: V → Y	TLB: V → X PTE: V → Y
7	C: Update PTE	TLB: N/A PTE: V → Y	TLB: N/A PTE: V → Y				↑ Inconsistent
8	P/C: Access V	TLB: V → Y PTE: V → Y	TLB: V → Y PTE: V → Y				

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Migrating a page of the parent process (a) With per-process private page table. (b) With shared page table.

Some memory management mechanisms (e.g., memory compaction, swap and NUMA balance) in Linux will migrate a page of the process to a new page frame or swap the page to the disk. In these cases, the PTE is changed but the data remains unchanged.

Take Fig 1(a) as an example, there are two processes (the parent process and its child process). The figure shows the real-time status of the PTE and the entry cached in the TLB. “V” represents a virtual address. “X” and “Y” represent two different physical addresses. “V → N” indicates that the PTE is none present.

When the operating system (OS) decides to migrate the page located on “X”, the process of the migration is described as follows: 1) Traverse all virtual address which is mapped to “X” and set the PTE to be none present while flushing the TLB (Step 2 to Step 5). Allocate a new physical page (“Y”) and copy the data from “X” to “Y”, then update the PTE (Step 6 and Step 7). After that, both parent process and child process can still access “V” to get the original data.

The problem arises when the processes share the page table. Take Fig 1(b) as an example. Migrating the page on “X” leads to “V → N” in the parent process (Step 2). However, the child process also has “V → N” in its page table because the two process are sharing the page table. The child process will be skipped since its virtual address “V” is not mapped to “X” (Step 4). As the result, the TLB will not be flushed. Finally, when the child process accesses “V”, it loses the original data. **Even worse, if “X” is used by another process,**

the data on “X” can be accessed illegally by the child process.

We provide an example program (*tlb_vulnerability.c* in the hub) to actually demonstrate this problem.

3 (Reviewer C) PTE Copy-on-write in the Parent Process

Figure 2: The histogram of the PTE copy-on-write in *ACF* and *ODF* under different Redis instance sizes.

To understand why *ACF* outperforms *ODF*, we record the interruption of the parent process (Redis) during the snapshot process.

For *ACF*, the interruption is caused by the proactive PTE copy. For *ODF* the interruption is caused by setting up private PTEs. From the perspective of implementation, both *ACF* and *ODF* use *copy_pmd_range()* to achieve the above operation (We name the operation as “PTE copy-on-write” for short). Specifically, we record the number of *copy_pmd_range()* invocations and the duration of each invocation in the parent process. We show the results in the histogram as shown in Fig. 2. Note that Fig. 12 of our manuscript shows the total duration of PTE copy-on-write. **As we can see, the parent has much fewer PTE copy-on-write with *ACF* than with *ODF*.**

4 (Reviewer C + E) Disabling Background Threads

Fig. 3 shows the maximum latency during the snapshot process under different Redis instance sizes. “*ACF-#1*” represents the results of disabling all background threads in *ACF*. **As we can see, *ACF* still reduces the maximum latency compared with *ODF* (34.3% on average).** Besides, using additional 7 threads (“*ACF-#8*”), which helps the child process copy PTEs faster,

Figure 3: The maximum latency during snapshot process.

can further reduce the maximum latency. The background threads are optional; enabling more threads is recommended when the CPU resources are adequate.

5 (Reviewer D + E) The Impact of the Page Copy-on-write

The Page copy-on-write is not the main factor that causes latency spike during the snapshot. Because the workloads of IMKVSEs tend to have random rather than contiguous memory access patterns, the page copy-on-write will not happen continuously. However, copying PTEs is executed continuously and causes denial-of-service for a long time.

To quantify the impact of the page copy-on-write, we conduct the experiment: using standard *fork* to take the snapshot in a 64GB Redis instance, while using the benchmark described in Section 3.1 of our manuscript to generate the write-intensive workload. We start to record the latencies of queries when the child process starts to persist data. Note that after the child process is created by the standard *fork*, there is no PTE copying but only page copy-on-write in the parent process.

We observe that the maximum latency of those queries is 8.49ms, while the maximum latency during normal operation is 5.76ms. The result indicates that page copy-on-write is not the main culprit of low performance of parent process.

6 (Reviewer D) Response to Other Comments

1. In Fig. 3 of our manuscript, dark blue represents PGD/P4D/PUD and light blue represents PMD/PTE.
2. Enabling additional kernel threads will interfere the performance of the IMKVS when CPU resources are shortage. Kernel threads are optional.
3. Redis adopts multiple threads while only one thread is used to handle queries. The number of IMKVS threads does not affect *ACF*.

4. In Fig. 13 of our manuscript, *ACF* performs differently on Redis and KeyDB possibly due to different implementations between Redis and KeyDB. Besides, we use Memtier as the workload generator. Since Memtier is a close-loop generator, it ignores the queuing time of queries in the client. As the result, the difference in reported latencies is not significant.
5. *ODF* is not deployed in production so there is no corresponding result reported in Section 10.7 of our manuscript.

7 (Reviewer E) Throughput Results with Standard Fork

Figure 4: (a) The changes of throughput during snapshot process in a 16GB Redis Server. (b) The minimum throughput during snapshot process under different Redis instance sizes.

Fig. 4(a) shows the processing throughput of a 16GB Redis server. The processing throughput is reported for every 50 milliseconds. As we can see, the throughput drops to 0 for a time with standard *fork*. This is because the parent process stops serving for about 200ms when calling standard *fork*. Fig. 4(b) shows the minimum processing throughput under different Redis instance sizes. The minimum throughput is 0 when the instance size is larger than 2GB with standard *fork*.

References

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